

PartitonNet: a way of partitioning unstructured data

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Introduction

The naming of PartitonNet is inspired by the “Partiton” (also known as Sharding) in the distributed database. In the distributed database, a record is stored on specific server according to a certain partition (or sharding) rule of the primary key. When retrieving a record by its primary key, the database system only need to perform calculations through the same partitioning rules to figure out which server stores the record, without having to perform a query to each server in advance.

For structured data (such as the primary key of a database), mature partitioning rules are available. However, for unstructured data, can we partition the data? If we can partition these data, then it will bring about an improvement in the amount of calculation. The following example of face recognition will explain the problem.

In the actual application of face recognition, face photos are converted into embedding (for example, a 512-dimensional vector) and stored in the database. To perform face lookup, the only thing need to do is comparing the new embedding with the existing embeddings in the database.

However, with huge amount of face embeddings in the database, there will be an overhead in the calculation complexity.

If faces could be partitioned by a certain partitioning algorithm, then we can optimize the complexity of calculation in the lookup phase. The following points explains the process in detail: 1. At the stage of saving faces to database, calculate the partition information of each face. 2. In the face lookup phase, calculate the partition of the input face. 3. Only compare the data in the partition with the input face.

In addition, in other fields where embeddings are used, partitioning can decrease the calculation as well.

PartitionNet

Requirements of Partitioning Algorithm

From the case of face recognition, what requirements should a suitable partitioning algorithm meet? 1. Accuracy. Two faces of the same person must be located in the same partition as much as possible. 2. Sparsity. The faces of different people should be distributed as sparsely as possible in the space. The sparser the distribution, the

smaller the number of faces in each partition and the smaller the amount of calculation.

Accuracy

The input of PartitionNet is a face image, and the output is a 3-dimensional vector.

To ensure accuracy, we should keep the distance of the same person's face in the 3-dimensional space as small as possible.

PartitionNet uses Euclidean distance as one of the loss items to achieve this requirement.

Sparsity

PartitionNet's limitation of sparsity is inspired by the electromagnetic force of three-dimensional space.

Suppose that several positive charges are placed in a hollow sphere of a fixed size. These positive charges will move under the action of electromagnetic force and converge to a stable equilibrium state.

In the stable equilibrium state, the distribution of the charge in the sphere is relatively uniform.

So, to make 3-dimensional vectors of the faces to reach this state, what kind of loss function should be used?

We continue to analyze the nature of stable equilibrium. In a stable equilibrium state, according to the principle of minimum potential energy, the potential energy of the system is the smallest. (In this system, it refers to electric potential energy)

Therefore, the goal we want to optimize is **electric potential energy**.

$$E = k \frac{Qq}{r}$$

Ignoring other constant terms, the potential energy can be expressed by one divided by the distance.

$$E = c \frac{1}{r}$$

And because the total potential energy of the system is equal to the sum of the potential energy of each pair of charges.

$$E = c * \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{1}{r(i,j)}$$

According to the above formula, our training strategy is: **Randomly sample 2 different people's face photos each time for training. The model outputs a 3-**

dimensional vector for each person's face. Take one divided by the distance of the three-dimensional vector pair as one of the loss terms.

This training strategy ensures that our optimization target is the total potential energy of the system.

Network Architecture

We use the pre-trained facenet as the backbone, plus a few convolutional layers, and finally GlobalAveragePooling. See the code for the detailed structure. The pre-trained model comes from [3], and the model class is also extended on its basis (Inception Resnet V1).

The output of the network is a three-dimensional vector.

Training

Face images are all preprocessed by the "PreWhiten" method proposed by facenet.

In the training phase, our input data is also "Triplet": 3 faces (A, P, N). A and P come from the same person, and N comes from different people.

The selection of A, P, and N is carried out randomly. Unlike facenet training, we will not deliberately choose the harder (A, P, N) to let the network learn faster. Facenet needs to distinguish two people who look alike, while the task of PartitionNet is relatively simple. It only needs to put the face of the same person in the same partition and make the distribution of faces of different people sparse.

The loss function consists of 2 parts: 1. The Euclidean distance of A and P (may be powered by some number) $c1 * Dist(A, P)^{N1}$ 2. The distances of A and N are inversely proportional (may be powered by some number). This is also part of the potential energy mentioned above. $c2 * \frac{1}{Dist(A, P)^{N2}}$

Among them, $c1, c2, N1, N2$ are all tunable hyperparameters. Because we cannot directly optimize our goal (the proportion of faces contained in the partition), we can only use this indirect method.

We use the SGD optimizer, BATCH_SIZE = 64, momentum=0.9, nesterov=True, weight_decay=0 for training.

The initial learning rate is 1e-2. When the loss stops falling, the learning rate is multiplied by a factor of 1/10 until reaching 1e-4.

Evaluation

How to evaluate the performance of PartitionNet for partitioning? The discussion is divided into two stages, Stage1 and Stage2.

Stage 1

Premise: For the convenience of discussion, we assume that there is only one face information of each person in the database.

The task of stage 1 is to estimate: **If you want to ensure that the hit rate is X%, what search radius should we use.**

*Hit rate explanation: Now there is a face that needs to be recognized. We first use our model to calculate its three-dimensional coordinate $P1$. **Hit rate** is the probability that this person's face is contained in a sphere with $P1$ as the center of the sphere and $dist$ as the radius.*

Process in detail:

1. In the data set, randomly select a person who has multiple photos.
2. Randomly select 2 photos of this person. The reason of selecting 2 photos is one of them represents the original photos in the database, and the other represents the input photos.
3. Use our model to calculate the coordinates of these two photos in a 3-dimensional space, and then calculate the distance.
4. Repeat this experiment many times to get multiple distance values, and then we are able to estimate the distance distribution. By sorting these distance values and taking the distances d_{99} , d_{98} ... at the 99%, 98%... index of the array, we can estimate **the search radius to use to reach 99%, 98%... accuracy.**

Stage 2

In stage1, we know the requirements of the search radius under a certain hit rate requirement.

In stage2, the item we want to estimate is: **When we search for a face with a certain search radius, how many times do we need to compare on average?** (The proportion of the number of faces that need to be compared)

Process: 1. For each person in the data set, select 1 photo to form our new data set. 2. Calculate the three-dimensional coordinates of each photo in the data set. 3. For each photo, we delineate a sphere with a radius of $dist$ around its three-dimensional coordinates, and then find how many photos are inside this sphere. 4. In the actual application scene, to determine whether a certain point is in the sphere or not, additional calculations will be required, and there is no database index support as well. So, we changed the sphere to a cube with original radius as its side length. We count the number of pictures inside this cube. **This cube is the partition we delineated.** 5. Take the average and get the average number of images (embedding) that need to be compared as our performance evaluation criteria.

Experiment

We trained on CASIA and LFW datasets respectively.

The proportion of training set and test set are both 60% : 40%.

HitRate	Calculation (CASIA)	Calculation (LFW)
99.9%	93.63%	70.80%
99%	63.50%	46.24%
98%	52.80%	36.04%
97%	48.03%	31.58%
96%	44.41%	28.18%
95%	41.81%	25.69%
94%	39.55%	23.65%
93%	37.68%	21.80%
92%	36.04%	20.53%
91%	34.50%	18.42%
90%	33.07%	16.75%
88%	30.68%	15.05%
85%	27.66%	12.24%
80%	23.73%	9.30%
75%	20.50%	7.02%
70%	17.74%	5.11%
60%	13.43%	2.85%
50%	10.02%	1.48%

In real life applications scene, if the face photos in the database are high-quality photos (similar to the LFW data set), then our performance will be closer to the performance on LFW.

In addition, we can notice that when the hit rate is 50%, the LFW calculation complexity is only 1.48%. We assume the following scenario in a practical application: there is a surveillance camera on a certain road section, taking a picture every second and performing face lookup. Pedestrians walks through this section of the road will take a certain amount of time, so multiple photos (and at different angles) will be taken. Even if each photo has a 50% chance of hitting, since we have multiple photos, our hit rate is $(1 - 0.5^N)$. Of course, this also depends on the correlation between the hit rate and the photo quality, angle, and identity of the photo (in the worst case, the hit rate is completely related to the person's identity, and 50% of people will never be hit). Detailed result needs additional testing to acquire.

Anyway, PartitionNet provides different granularities of computational savings for scenarios with different accuracy requirements.

Improvement Space

The hyper parameters and structure of the model still have a lot of room for tuning, because our model quickly (within an hour) converged to the values we reported in this article.

In addition, our loss is not a direct estimation of our evaluation criteria. More experiments needs to be done to find the optimal hyperparameter.

Related work

Facebook's faiss is a vector search tool. It works in the embedding space.

The PartitionNet is different, the output is a three-dimensional vector.

Embedding space has a lot of redundancy: in embedding space, we can find faces that belongs to the same person as the target face, or find faces that are more similar or not very similar through distance. This redundancy also brings difficulties in optimizing the amount of calculation.

Our 3-dimensional space does not have distance requirements for the faces of different people, but only requires a sparse distribution (this means that the faces of two similar people can be very close). This is also an indication of the low redundancy to our 3-dimensional space.

In addition, PartitonNet provides a variety of calculation complexity corresponding to the hit rate, which can be more adaptive to the face search tasks under different accuracy requirements. In the case of low accuracy requirements, the calculation complexity can be greatly optimized.

Reference

[1] Schroff, Florian et al. "FaceNet: A unified embedding for face recognition and clustering." 2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) (2015): 815-823.

[2] Johnson, J. et al. "Billion-scale similarity search with GPUs." ArXiv abs/1702.08734 (2017): n. pag.